

THE PHENOMENON OF GRADUONYMY IN UZBEK LANGUAGE LINGUISTICS

Urakova Shoira

teacher of Termiz State University

E-mail: urakovashaira@gmail.com

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Abstract: It is obvious to everyone that all events and formations in nature and society are inextricably linked. In particular, units of language science are closely related to each other, they have similarities and differences. Some of their properties have been studied, while others are still waiting for their research. We can safely say this about the phenomena of graduonymy and synonymy.

Keywords: synonymy, antonymy, polysemantic, graduonymy, paradigm, microsystem, numerical word, "Muhokamat ul-lughatayn", verb, gradation

It is known that the Uzbek language has very rich possibilities and has an ancient history. Therefore, it is necessary to look for the roots of our language from very ancient times. Alisher Navoi's initial views on the leveling are in part. We also find it in the work "Muhokamat-ul-lughatayn". In our linguistics, synonyms have been sufficiently studied, their properties have been proven by certain scientific researches. But the phenomenon of graduonymy has not been studied to the extent required. The phenomenon of graduonymy as a type of lexeme-semantic relations has been considered since the end of the 80s. Until this time, the phenomenon of gradation was studied within the framework of synonyms. The main reason for this was that words with the characteristic of gradation were given as synonyms in the dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language. After researching this issue, it was learned that graduonymy and synonymy are not the same phenomenon, and the graduable words were distributed into synonymy nests.

Synonymous series is formed by combining the members of the paradigm around one common denotant. In this case, the meaning between the members of the paradigm, the event-events, signs-characteristics, which they name, name represent exactly one concept. They can be distinguished in their paradigm according to stylistic colors and scope of application. The word graduonymy as a linguistic term was first used by R. Safarova and the authors of "Theses of System Lexicology". The essence of lexical graduonymy is manifested in the arrangement of several words in a lexical meaningful line depending on the abundance of a certain sign. In most cases, lexical graduonymic series unite around a single leading word (dominant) and fully meet all the requirements for lexical meaning groups.

The members of the graduonymic paradigm, in contrast to the members of the synonymous series, do not rate a specific concept, but a certain concept. In this case, the quantitative sign is graded according to the characteristic of increasing or decreasing between the members of the paradigm. Graduonymy is the phenomenon of mental gradation in the general sense. Graduonymy is not a phenomenon of today, but a few centuries ago, the great scholar of our literature A. Navoi, in his work "Muhokamat ul-lughatayn", a discussion of two languages dedicated to the field of linguistics, for the first time, there is a phenomenon of gradation in linguistics. said that it will grow depending on the level. It is obvious to everyone that all

things and events in existence are inextricably linked with each other. In particular, all units in the language are closely related, they have similarities and differences. Some of their properties have been studied, while others are still waiting for their research. We can safely say this about the phenomena of graduonymy and synonymy. If synonymy and its specific aspects have been studied a lot, the phenomenon of graduonymy has not been studied to the extent required. Even though synonomic relations have a long history in the history of linguistics, like our science, even though thousands and thousands of pages and works have been devoted to the problems of lexical semantics, even though not one, but several dictionaries of synonyms have been compiled, in the problem of synonyms, there are still many puzzles that need to be solved.

The study of graduonymy (semantic gradation) as a special type of semantic relations between words began in the late 80s. In linguistics, until graduonymy was distinguished as a special form of semantic relations between words, a series of words expressing a sign by degree were studied within the framework of synonyms. In the dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language, the words whose meaning is graded were given among synonyms in many cases. Of course, since the phenomenon of graduonymy was not specifically distinguished, the words indicating the meaning of the degree were in most cases scattered in different synonomic nests. There were also legitimate reasons for this. Because synonyms include words that are close to each other in meaning. It should be emphasized that since the language is a system, the vocabulary system also has a systematic nature, and there is no word (lexeme) in the language that does not have a place in a certain lexical paradigm. The phenomenon of spiritual leveling was not specifically distinguished, and since the words that level the meaning were in most cases absorbed into the synonyms, for example, the words whispering~talking~shouting could not be included in the dictionary of synonyms. The main factor of distinguishing synonyms and combining words into synonomic paradigms is what synonyms mean, what they name, what they name is the exactness of a thing, an event, a sign, a feature. This sharp difference separates graduonymy from synonymy.

The leading factor in combining synonomic lines is that the words of the synonomic paradigm have one common denotation (so-called), and within their paradigm they differ mainly by stylistic colors, the scope of use, while the words of the graduonymic paradigm have different denotations. but the difference between these denotations is not in the qualities of the denotations, but in their quantities. Therefore, the main difference between synonymy and graduonymy can be shown as follows: the members of the paradigm of words connected by synonymous relations call, express and name the same reality in different ways. Members of the paradigm of words associated with graduonymic relations are associated with relations of increasing or decreasing the same sign in different denotations. At first glance, the line between synonymy and graduonymy seems to be clear - if the denotations are the same - synonymy, if the denotations are different, these denotations are mutual adjectives, as well as the meaning of the words. if the amount is different - graduonymy. When distinguishing the synonomic series, the linguists' base point is the meaning of the words and the rotation of the reality that these words denote; In graduonymic lexical lines, the meaning of the words, as well as the quantitative indicators in the semantic constructions of these words, are different at the level of the same sign. Grading can be an event between lexemes, inter-phrases, and between lexemes and phrases. Based on these, it is appropriate to talk about lexical and phraseological graduonymy. Lexical graduonymy is reflected in special graduonymic lines.

Therefore, it is necessary to think about the relationship between the units and the relationships between these units.

The most important building block of a gradation series is the increase or decrease of the amount of a common character in it. Therefore, lexemes and phrases in this line form mutual semantic links (connections) according to the singular-plural level of one common sign. The main factor in the structure of the gradunomic series is the fact that one type of semantic sign, with its increase or decrease, has become stable components, components of various lexemes and phrases. Therefore, a lexical hierarchy can consist of two or more units. Graduonymy is actually evident in the three-membered series. Nevertheless, we should take into account that the sequence (event) can have two members from the linguistic point of view.

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